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DECLARAÇÃO DE BERLIM

ATÉ ALCANÇAR UM MODELO HUMANO DE POLÍTICAS DE DROGAS

A atual guerra contra as drogas se tornou uma espiral cada vez mais destrutiva. Os princípios em que se baseia a proibição tem fracassado totalmente. A tentativa de um mundo sem drogas, através da redução da oferta e da abstinência mediante a violência do Estado não estão de acordo com as realidades de cada continente e região, pois fomenta estruturas antidemocráticas, repressivas e autoritárias que fortalecem a influência econômica do crime organizado.

A guerra global contra as drogas conduz a violações sistemáticas dos direitos humanos, corrupção, aumento massivo no número de detenções e processos judiciais, além de aumentar significativamente os riscos sociais e de saúde das pessoas que usam drogas ilegalizadas.

A proibição é um caminho político errado que se transformou em uma ideologia mórbida. Enquanto a guerra contra as drogas cresce desmesuradamente no triângulo norte da América Central e do Sudeste Asiático semeando terrores e morte, o uso de substâncias ilegalizadas em âmbitos científicos e psicoterapêuticos e a descriminalização dos usuários de drogas avança em outras regiões aprofundando as incongruências do proibicionismo, demonstrando que os esforços da sociedade civil e da comunidade científica em matéria de incidência política e pública estão contribuindo para que as pessoas que usam drogas (PQU) tenham melhor qualidade de vida e aqueles que padecem do uso problemático possam acessar os serviços sociais e de saúde adequados através de políticas públicas concretas baseadas em metodologias de redução de danos.

Por isto, e ante o sofrimento de milhões de pessoas que padecem com as consequências da guerra contra as drogas, nós como homens e mulheres de diversas visões de mundo, cristãs, ativistas, livre-pensadores, defensores dos direitos humanos e usuários de drogas dirigimos esta exortação às Nações Unidas, ao Escritório das Nações Unidas para as Drogas e a Delinquência, à Comissão de Narcóticos e drogas, a União Europeia, a CICA, a OEA, a CELAC – Comunidade dos Estados Latino-americanos e Caribenhos, aos políticos, às igrejas, às comunidades e às organizações sociais:

Coloquem um fim a guerra contra as drogas. Estabeleçam um acordo de cumprimento do “processo conciliador pela paz, justiça e criação”, exortamos às organizações baseadas na fé, comunidades cristãs, agrupamentos laicos, associações civis, organismos internacionais e organizações sociais a defender ativamente o fim da guerra contra as drogas.

– Exortamos para o necessário aprofundamento da cooperação judicial para o combate real ao crime organizado, à lavagem de dinheiro, e ao bloqueio de divisas.

Reforçamos que é necessário:

- Promover e analisar novas propostas alternativas à proibição e à repressão como política.
- Implementar a prevenção do abuso e educação relativa às drogas baseadas em estratégias de redução de danos e riscos desde uma perspectiva dos Direitos Humanos.
- Promover e ocupar os espaços para a sociedade civil no processo Pós-UNGASS.
- Financiamento de campanhas internacionais que incluam informação sobre as políticas de drogas internacionais e locais, informação para a prevenção e educação validadas com dados científicos honestos, desprovidos de preconceito e mitificação dos usuários de drogas e das próprias substâncias.

Que se reconheça a privacidade dos usuários de drogas para decidir livremente suas condutas de vidas e autodeterminação;

As instituições e pessoas assinam abaixo:

Nos comprometemos a impulsionar uma reforma ao atual modelo de fiscalização internacional de drogas que se sustenta em aspectos sociais, de saúde e de direitos humanos. Esta reforma deveria focar-se em sanar as consequências negativas das políticas atuais

Nos comprometemos a impulsar una reforma ao atual modelo de fiscalização internacional de drogas que se sustenta em aspectos sociais, de saúde e de direitos humanos.

Esta reforma deveria focar-se em resolver as consequências negativas das atuais políticas, prevenir o consumo abusivo de todo tipo de substâncias psicoativas e alcólicas e combater o grande narcotráfico.

Unidos na Diversidade, em concordância com a justiça e o amor que nos move, afirmamos que:

A Guerra Não deve ser Contra As Drogas!

Initiators

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Nós convidamos você a se juntar e nos apoiar na construção do
futuro que todos nós merecemos.

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